

Metal Complexes of *N,N'*-Bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea

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Reaction of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with a new Mannich base *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea (L) yielded metal complexes having stoichiometry, $2M.L.4H_2O$. The ligand coordinated with the metal ion through the two amide nitrogens of the urea moiety and through ring nitrogens of the two morpholine entities. All the complexes contained four coordinated water molecules. Preliminary antimicrobial screening showed that the ligand and complexes possess antimicrobial activities.

Urea and related compounds have been investigated in detail for their donor properties and biological activities¹. We have reported the metal complexes with morpholinomethylurea, a Mannich base of urea, morpholine and formaldehyde condensation².

Aldehydes other than formaldehyde were reported to be used to a lesser extent in the condensations of Mannich reactions^{3,7}. We report herein the synthesis of a new Mannich base, *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea using urea, morpholine and benzaldehyde, and its metal complexes with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni and Cu. The biological activities of the ligand and the complexes have been studied.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometries of the complexes proposed are supported by the chemical analysis and electrical conductance data (Table 1). All the complexes are stable in air and non-hygroscopic. However, the colour of the Cu^{II} complexes changed on exposure to air. They are soluble in polar organic solvents but insoluble in water and non-polar organic solvents. The Cu^{II} complexes when added to water, immediately decomposed releasing a benzaldehyde odour.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	λ_{max} cm^{-1}	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$
$2MnCl_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	22 480	15 59
$2Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	25 865, 22 685	14 61
$2MnSO_4 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	26 145, 23 487	49 36
$2Mn(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	26 976, 24 675	7 84
$2CoCl_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	19 420, 17 930	19 61
$2CoBr_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	20 120	11 35
$2CoSO_4 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	20 750, 16 300	37 84
$2Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	19 870	9 67
$Co(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	19 640, 18 970	18 95
$2NiCl_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	25 750, 15 690	11 69
$2NiBr_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	24 430, 17 940	17 65
$2NiSO_4 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	26 360, 16 900	37 28
$2Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	24 460, 15 670	29 15
$2Ni(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	25 290, 15 520	18 31
$2CuCl_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	11 650, 15 791	22 19
$2CuSO_4 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	12 345, 16 449, 28 941	42 16
$2Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	12 576, 14 978, 29 376	19 30
$2Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L \cdot 4H_2O$	12 856, 15 730, 30 291	16 85

Molar conductance : The observed molar conductance values of manganese(II) complexes are in the range $7.84-49.36 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$. Since the value for 1 : 1 electrolyte in DMF is of the order of $65-90 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$, it is concluded that the anions are covalently bonded to manganese(II) ion⁴. Electrical conductivity values of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be much less than that expected for 1 : 1 electrolyte, suggesting all the complexes to be non-electrolytes.

Magnetic properties : Generally it is found that the majority of the Mn^{II} complexes are of high-spin⁵.

In the present case, the experimentally determined room temperature magnetic moments of the Mn^{II} complexes lie in the range 5.56–5.65 B.M., proving the high-spin nature of these complexes. The Co^{II} complexes show magnetic moment values ranging from 4.59 to 5.15 B.M. indicating a six-coordinated environment around the central metal ion, since high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes show magnetic moment in the range 4.7–5.2 B.M. which is higher than the spin-only value of 3.89 B.M. due to the orbital contribution. In octahedral and slightly tetragonally distorted octahedral fields of nickel(II) complexes two unpaired electrons are present. Since the ground state makes no orbital contribution to the magnetic moment, these moments are expected to be not greatly different from the spin-only moment of 2.83 B.M. The observed magnetic moment values of the Ni^{II} complexes (3.26–3.39 B.M.) thus suggest octahedral geometry around the metal centre. The room temperature magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes are in the range 1.08–1.35 B.M. except for the sulphato complex. These subnormal magnetic moment values can arise due to antiferromagnetic spin-pairing between the two paramagnetic copper(II) ions. The complex with copper(II) sulphate is found to have a magnetic moment value of 1.81 B.M., thereby showing the absence of copper-copper interaction which is also supported by esr data (G value).

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectral data for all the complexes are listed in Table I. Manganese(II) complexes exhibit two weak bands in the range 21 000–27 000 cm^{-1} . Most of the salts and complexes of manganese(II) in which the ion finds itself in octahedral surroundings are very pale pink since all the excited states of the d^5 systems are spin-forbidden⁶. In the present case, all the Mn^{II} complexes are pale pink in colour indicating six-coordinated octahedral geometry. The observed absorption maxima of the pink coloured Co^{II} complexes are in agreement with those for the following three spin allowed $d-d$ transitions : ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ which arise in an octahedral field. The band in the visible region near 20 000 cm^{-1} is assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transition.

The bands of the green coloured Ni^{II} chloro complex observed at 25 750 and 15 690 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions respectively. The possible absorption below 11 000 cm^{-1} was not recorded due to the limitation of the instrument. The Ni^{II} bromo complex has absorptions at 24 430 and 17 940 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to ν_3 and ν_2 bands respectively. The Ni^{II} sulphato, nitrate and perchlorato complexes also exhibit similar types of bands. All these bands are characteristic of a nickel(II) complex in octahedral (tetragonal) environment. All the Co^{II} complexes exhibit broad absorption at 11 500–12 500 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition indicating the effect of Jahn-Teller distortion. Thus, all the Cu^{II} complexes are understood to have the distorted octahedral geometry around copper(II) ion. In addition, the Cu^{II} sulphato, nitrate and perchlorato complexes have strong absorption around 29 000–30 000 cm^{-1} due to charge transfer. The electronic spectra rule out tetrahedral structure for the Cu^{II} complexes since usually they show no $d-d$ bands in the range 10 000–20 000 cm^{-1} .

Infrared spectra : The ligand exhibited three bands of strong intensity at 3 330 (NH), 1 635 (C=O) and 1 130 cm^{-1} (C–N–C). In all the complexes, the ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ bands displayed substantial negative shifts with considerable low intensity, indicating coordination through the nitrogens of the urea moiety and nitrogens of the two morpholine entities present in the ligand. The ir spectra of all the complexes show no change in the positions of the absorption bands of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O-C}}$ suggesting non-involvement of carbonyl oxygen and ring oxygen on coordination. The bands around 3 500–3 450, 1 640–1 620, 720–875 and 610–660 cm^{-1} indicate presence of coordinated water in the complexes⁷. In the Mn^{II} nitrate complexes, the anion exhibits unidentate coordination since ($\nu_5-\nu_1$) is 75 cm^{-1} . Normally the difference expected for a bidentate nitrate group is around 185 cm^{-1} . For this complex, ν_2 band is seen around 1 050 cm^{-1} . Absorptions due to the bidentate sulphato group in the Mn^{II} complex appear at 1 140, 1 090 and 1 025 (ν_3) and 635 cm^{-1} (ν_4). In the Mn^{II} perchlorato complex, (Cl–O) stretching frequencies of unidentate perchlorato group exhibit ν_3 bands at 1 150, 1 185

(ν_3) and 900 cm^{-1} (ν_4). The band around $1\ 150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ normally appears as a split band (doublet) and is little broad because of overlapping with (C–N–C) stretching vibration of the heterocyclic ring. Only in the case of the Co^{II} chloro complex δ_{OH} appears at $1\ 615\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In all other complexes, this band overlaps with the strong carbonyl absorption band which makes it difficult to assign the absorption due to δ_{OH} . The bands at 390 and 499 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectrum of the Ni^{II} bromo complex can be ascribed to $\nu_{\text{Ni-Br}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ vibrations respectively⁷. Presence of coordinated nitrate, sulphate and perchlorate groups are also evident from the ir spectra. The absorption band at 320 cm^{-1} observed in the case of the Cu^{II} chloro complex is due to $\nu_{\text{Cu-Cl}}$ vibrations; $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ appears at 426 cm^{-1} . In the nitrate complex, the bands at 335 and 285 cm^{-1} may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band of the sulphato and perchlorato complexes appear at 440 and 529 cm^{-1} respectively. The bands at 290 cm^{-1} for the sulphato complex and at 249 cm^{-1} for the perchlorato complex may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations.

Esr spectra : The esr spectra of the Cu^{II} nitrate, sulphato and perchlorato complexes exhibit two g values at room temperature indicating the overall symmetry to be tetragonal around the copper(II) ion. But the esr spectra recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature for the complexes of copper(II) sulphate and perchlorate show only one g value, i.e. g_{iso} . Kivelson and Neiman⁸ demonstrated that for covalent environment g_{\parallel} is less than 2.3 and for ionic environment this is usually 2.3 or greater. In all the three Cu^{II} complexes, the g_{\parallel} values are less than 2.3, indicating that the complexes are largely covalent. Further, the complexes show esr spectra with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. From the observed g value it is evident that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the d_{x-y} orbital. In the perchlorato and nitrate complexes, the G values are found to be less than 4 suggesting the presence of an exchange interaction in solid state between the two copper centres. G value for the copper(II) sulphato complex indicates no interaction between two metal centres.

Thermal studies : The TG curves of Mn^{II} chloro and sulphato complexes show weight-loss in 135 – 175° and 120 – 165° regions respectively, correspond-

ing to the loss of four coordinated water molecules. In the case of the chloro complex the final stable product was identified as MnO . It also showed a strong endothermic peak at 150° indicating the loss of water. The sulphato complex showed a medium intensity endothermic peak at 140° and a strong endothermic peak at 260° which are due to the loss of coordinated water and the melting of the complex respectively. The nickel(II) sulphato complex showed a decomposition step in the region 125 – 170° corresponding to the loss of four coordinated water and the respective broad endothermic peak was obtained at 160° . A strong endothermic peak at 390° may be due to the melting of the complex. In the copper(II) sulphato complex, the decomposition step at 120 – 175° in TG curve and the sharp endothermic DTA peak at 170° were indicative of the presence of four coordinated water molecules. The DTA pattern showed two exothermic peaks at 340 and 520° which are due to the oxidative process. The weight of the final product at 700° corresponds to CuO .

Antimicrobial activity : In all the compounds tested, the antimicrobial activity was found to increase with increasing concentration of the compounds. In most of the cases, the compounds were less active towards *S. aureus* than towards *P. aeruginosa* showing that former has more resisting power than the latter. The values of percentage inhibition of bacterial growth also showed that all the complexes are more active than the ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solvents used were purified by standard methods. Spectroscopic grade solvents (B.D.H.) were used for spectral measurements. Metal salts were used as such without dehydrating them.

Synthesis of ligand : In the preparation of *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea, urea, morpholine and benzaldehyde were reacted in 1 : 2 : 2 mole ratio. Urea was dissolved in minimum amount of distilled water. To this solution, morpholine followed by benzaldehyde were added and the contents stirred well. The mixture turned oily and was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 h. The resulting white crystalline solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 169 – 71° .

Synthesis of complexes : Since the ligand is insoluble in water, all the complexes were prepared in non-aqueous media. Manganese(II) complexes were prepared by digesting (~15 min) the butanolic solution containing the ligand and the Mn^{II} salt in 1:1 mole ratio. The solution was concentrated, cooled and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and acetone and dried at 100°. Co^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing the alcoholic solution of the ligand and the metal salt. The solution was then concentrated and kept overnight. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried at 100°. The ligand and Co^{II} chloride, bromide and nitrate salts were dissolved in n-butanol, while Co^{II} sulphate and perchlorate were dissolved in methanol. Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were prepared by mixing hot n-butanol solution of the metal salt and ligand except in the case of Ni^{II} perchlorate, Cu^{II} sulphate and Cu^{II} perchlorate where methanol was used as the solvent. Ni^{II} sulphate was dissolved in minimum amount of DMF. While preparing the complex, in all the cases, the ligand solution was added to the metal salt solution. It was observed that even though all the complexes were of 2 : 1 type, a reaction mixture containing metal and ligand in 2 : 1 ratio resulted in poor yield. However, from a reaction mixture containing metal and ligand in 1 : 1 ratio, an appreciable yield of the complex was obtained.

The metal and anion present in the complexes were estimated by standard procedures⁹. C, H and N were determined by CHN analyser.

Antimicrobial activities of the ligand and several of its complexes were carried out with test organisms, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* employing serial tube dilution technique¹⁰.

The molar conductance was measured using ~ 10⁻³ M solution in DMF on a Systronics 304 conductivity meter at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at room temperature. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Jasco UVIDEc-430B spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆/CDCl₃) on a Bruker WH-270 FT NMR spectrometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-4 X-band spectrometer. Thermal data were obtained using a Shimadzu thermal analyser.

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